

METHODOLOGY OF INNOVATIVE USE OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE MATERIAL FOR CONSTRUCTION APPLICATION

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Abstract: The Republic of North Macedonia abounds in secondary raw materials in the form of industrial waste, construction & demolition waste and municipal services waste. As such, they represent a relatively unexplored potential for the market sector of raw materials and could be a significant source of secondary raw materials (SRM), which with some treatment and processing could be used in construction sector. The CINDERELA pilot project addresses this challenge by assessing industrial waste to the possibilities for resources, development and testing of new construction materials based on secondary raw materials and their application in construction. Based on analyzing the technical, technological, and administrative possibilities of processing of the slag and its reuse, construction material based on SRM has been developed. As the waste is not suitable for direct use in construction, it must be mechanically processed (sowing, demetalization, crushing, and mixing of the black slag and grinding and mixing of the white slag) into construction materials – aggregates. The final products are aggregate for a tampon (sub-base 0-63 mm), aggregate for asphalt (4-8 mm, 8-11 mm, 11-16 mm and 16-22 mm) and white slag as a 20% substitute for cement in concrete mixtures. These products can be used for revitalization of degraded areas, for asphaltting roads, for production of partition blocks for walls construction, etc. Their application will demonstrate the usefulness of industrial waste materials as new construction materials and the good practices that will help construction companies build circular business models.

Key words: industrial waste, secondary raw materials (SRM), reuse, circular economy, revitalization of degraded areas